

WHAT DOES “MODERN” MEAN?

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Abstract: this article provides detailed information about modern dance and its development today. Particular attention is paid to today's choreographic means of expression of modern dance.

Key words: dance, keljak, choreography, image, art

Contemporary dance and its individual directions are becoming increasingly independent in Uzbekistan. The popularity of modern dance is most clearly manifested among young people, which indicates its prospects for development in the future. This new artistic phenomenon, in the not distant future, will certainly occupy its own niche in the cultural life of Uzbekistan.

The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev in his work “Ensuring the rule of law and human interests is a guarantee of the development of the country and the well-being of the people” emphasized that “the current rapidly changing times, expanding globalization are opening up more and more new opportunities for humanity, especially youth” . In this regard, scientific research into the development of modern dance in Uzbekistan and teaching methods in the system of choreographic education become particularly relevant.

It should be noted that over the past three decades, modern dance in various forms of its implementation “in theaters, in amateur performances and in other stages” has gone through its own history of development. Of course, this story is not comparable in duration and significance with the history of the development of traditional Uzbek dance, but it is of undoubted interest, as it reflects modern trends in the development of culture in society. This accumulated artistic experience must be introduced into the creative and educational process. In this regard, there is an urgent need to conduct a scientific analysis, classification, generalizing research into the methods of teaching modern dance in choreographic art.

We use the word “Modern” a lot in different applications. Lately, in the combination “Modern dance”, what does this mean? What is “Modern Dance”? What elements make it up? And are there any? How is this phenomenon learned? And who are its bearers and performers? These are the questions that I would like to answer in this article.

The term “Modern”, which originally meant “Modern”, appeared along with a new direction in art at the turn of the 19th-20th centuries. This process also manifested itself in choreographic art, that is, in dance. The first manifestation of modernity in the ballet theater can be safely called the performances of Vaslav Nezhinsky. In the enterprise of Sergei Diaghilev.

The modern dance direction of the beginning of the 20th century is associated with the name of Ruth Saint-Denis, Martha Graham and their followers in America, Mary Bigman, the Wiesenthal Sisters, Rudolf Von Laban and their followers in Europe. The system – Methods of teaching modern dance – was developed and became the subject of training.

I believe that if you attract the most brilliant teachers, even if you master all the techniques, then your dance will not become modern, because it begins in the thoughts and in the heart, and not in the hands or feet. It is useful for different groups to meet on stage, because it is invisible, but it penetrates one to another. There are different paths, and it is not necessary to always be so open to the viewer. And it is very important for an educational institution to develop personality, to give students the opportunity to be who they want.

What is “Modern” dance? on the one hand, this is not a classic, on the other hand, we are asked to consider choreographies, for example, how balloons fly. And they say that this is also a dance. Here you still need to understand that not every movement is a dance.

I would like to say this, addressing first of all my colleagues and seminar participants. There is such a good truth. If you can't write, don't write; if you can't put it, it's better not to put it. Because my belief is that the task of people engaged in art is to create a new entity. And it is not the task of people to create additional emptiness. If you have nothing to bring to the audience, sit at home, in class, anywhere until the moment when you actually have something to bring and do something with me as a spectator. I want to come to the theater like this and leave as a different person, communicating with you. As far as education is concerned, training a choreographer. Pay attention, try to analyze what we talked about and thought about today. We think and talk about technology, technology and tools. And we completely forget that art is actually magic, and I don't know how to create people capable of creating this magic. Yes, everything is correct, knowledge is needed, knowledge is never superfluous. But it just doesn't work... today I can afford not to watch modern dance, because I feel like they are stealing my time, stealing my life. But at the same time, there are rare moments when that very magic happens. After all, the task of art is not only to

create something with the viewer now. You need to put a bomb in the viewer's pocket, which will explode somewhere after a while. If we now try to clarify the terminology of modern dance, everyone will answer in their own way. But it seems to me that in modern choreography it is, first of all, modern thinking.

The language of dance can be classical, neoclassical, contemporary, interpretation of all techniques and types. The quality of a choreographer's thinking for me determines whether this choreographer is modern or not. Otherwise, the situation arises when a society of the most worthy, most beautiful people gathers on the jury at competitions, each of whom has his own ideas about what is in modern choreography. And as a result, everything comes down to physical scoring. So I have a question; to what extent can these two worlds, which have very little contact, find a common language? I would like that people who are developing in the field of modern dance would become more consolidated, maybe they would take something from academic ballet as a basis and vice versa. Because these two incontinent systems, two independent planets need to take something from each other. Maybe this is precisely our task at the present stage in Russia, because in the world everything is already a little different. And this is understandable; the development of modern choreography did not stop there. And no one put up ideological barriers. If we developed classical and folk dance, but there was no modern, then everything goes on as usual... so for now we have a problem.

Indeed, there comes a time when the lack of development of theory affects practice.

The incomprehensibility of the term "Modern dance" with its many faces gives rise to a number of confusing pictures. He who knows how to analyze has the right to judge. We learn analysis from each other. This is a mutual process. Practice feeds into theory, and theory influences practice.

I would like to say that mutual respect and understanding is not a simple phenomenon. The nature of dance allows, moreover, suggests the emergence of ever new dance styles. The 20th century offered a large choice: jazz - dance and a response to the musical movement of jazz. Tap-dance, in Russia its variety is "Tap". Music - hall performances where different styles of dance were combined, especially its mass forms. Dances appeared and disappeared, influencing stage theater art. Some of them retained their form for a long time, these are "Charleston", "Woogie-woogie", "twist", "jive", "break". Many dances are influenced by national traditions of people's development. It is known that in history the most stable forms of dance arose at the junction of plastic motifs of

dances of a number of peoples, this was the case, for example, with the birth of the waltz in central Europe, or with the “tango”, which combined the motifs and rhythms of Spanish and Argentinean dance and mentality. I would like to explain by what criteria modern ballet is defined, as well as the value of those works that are shown on stage. Because art reflects life, and life becomes more complicated, we are bombarded with a large flow of information in all areas. This also affects the authors who create works in modern ballet. In my opinion, one of the criteria is the complication of vocabulary, an increase in the density of movement material per unit of time, including due to several points of perception. This is another system of complicating movement material, something that modern life and modern reality dictates - complications. What creates this intensity?

Firstly, due to the author's vocabulary, if a choreographer struggles and takes risks to create a work, then of course he first of all invents his own style, his own lexical language and this only becomes interesting within the framework of the competition.

Secondly, in my opinion, what defines modern ballet? It is a lack of narrative, a lack of telling a story in favor of movement. Abstractly - dance, but this does not mean that telling stories is prohibited. Each author decides for himself, I'm talking about trends. And one more point that defines modern ballet for me is the lack of illustrativeness, lack of inventiveness, including in emotional terms, emotions are experienced authentically, and not depicted, when this is not due to the facial expression of the face, but due to the complexity of the vocabulary that is present in the body of a dancer. The last point by which I characterized my ballet is the use of modern music. Dance is a reflection of life. The dance is a poem in it, every movement is a word, Mata Hara.

The word “modern” can be interpreted as associated with time, its rhythm and lifestyle. And how the dances perceived by contemporaries as their own correspond to their interests and tastes. Time passes, and they become only a characteristic of their time and lose the rights to the characteristic “modern”. This happened with Modern dance. Today, Modern dance is a specific direction that has its own classical examples. The concept of “Modern Classics” appeared. And to replace “modern” as “modern”, the term “contemporary” appeared. It characterizes the plastic styles of the late 20th and early 21st centuries. In other words, we can talk about a number of dances and styles included in this layer of culture of our time. They have their own characteristics, plastic motifs, musical rhythms. This means that there is no separate modern dance. And the styles of

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the times are very diverse and eclectic in the good sense of the word. The only alarming thing is the desire of the bearers of these styles to deny the general flow of the choreographic culture of the world, its diverse choreographic art, in which something new is born, in tune with its time. Search and creativity should not be aggressive - this is a positive process that arises and stable patterns, and they, in turn, will be tested by time and the best will become a characteristic of our time. A time when a huge stock of samples of classical, folk - stage, modern, sports, jazz - theatrical and mass forms of dance has been accumulated.

And together this is the modern culture of choreographic art - the property of the peoples of the world, an enduring value that does not need support in all its varieties. The nature of dance allows, moreover, suggests the emergence of ever new dance styles.

I would like to say that mutual respect and understanding is not a simple phenomenon. And everyone should understand that if he comes to an exhibition of impressionists and wants to judge him according to the laws of the Itinerants, then he will not like it. And if he comes to the Peredvizhniki and does not see what he loved from the Impressionists, he will be upset.

The examples we have given of teaching methods and techniques of modern dance abroad show the diversity and diversity of the “manifestations” of modern dance and the ways of teaching it in different schools in world art. The review also allows us to identify something in common that impoverishes all these teaching “technologies”. At the head of them all is always the personality of the choreographer - the artist, who every time creates his own new and original systems. Each such system can be created without regard to past traditions, since it is based on extensive practical experience. All these techniques are of great interest for the educational process, and they should be carefully studied and creatively comprehended in the context of pressing problems of the development of modern dance in the system of choreographic education in Uzbekistan.

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